

Industrial fermentation of hydrogen

Next generation biogas facilities

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Introduction

- Refineries are large-volume producers and consumers of hydrogen.
- Environmental regulations implemented in most countries, increase the hydrogen requirement at refineries for gas-line and diesel desulfurization.

Sources of hydrogen

Natural gas	48%
Hydrocarbons	30%
Coal	18%
Electrolysis	4%

- Oil-sands processing, gas-to-liquids and coal gasification projects that are ongoing, require a huge amount of hydrogen and is expected to boost the requirement significantly within the next few years.

Supply and demand

- 66% of all hydrogen is used in commercial fixation of nitrogen from the air to produce ammonia as a fertilizer.
- 33% of the hydrogen used is in; hydrogenation of fats and oils, methanol production, welding, hydrochloric acid production, metallic ore reduction, manufacturing of superconductors, manufacturing of semi-conductors, cooling turbines, fuel in the space program.
- The current estimated cost for production and delivery of 1m^3 hydrogen varies from \$555 to \$2.403, depending on location.

Fermentation

- Today's sustainable hydrogen techniques have an extensive energy requirement for electrolysis, since no suitable catalysis has been found to aid the production of hydrogen.
- Industrial fermentation of hydrogen requires a limited amount of energy, since catalysis is achieved with bacteria.
- Fermentation allows hydrogen to be produced from any organic material, since the process will not depend on the energy of substrate.

Fermentation

- Industrial fermentation of hydrogen depends on one or two of the following fermentation methods.

Dark-fermentation

Fermentation which depends on the energy of substrate. Only organic materials with a high energy content (etc. sugars) can be used in dark-fermentation.

Photo-fermentation

Fermentation which depends on light as the source of energy. Any organic material with a low energy content (etc. organic acids) can be used as substrate.

Dark-fermentation

Dark-fermentation

Treated sugar wastes are converted into hydrogen and organic acids by a mixed culture of *Clostridium*.

Photo-fermentation

Photo-fermentation

Organic acids are converted into hydrogen by the bacteria *Rhodobacter sphaeroides*.

Photo-fermentation

LED-fermenter

The photo-fermenter will use several rods coated with ultra-violet LED's to distribute the light within the fermenter to prevent self-shading.

Applications

- The implementation depends on the application. There are several options of application.

Agricultural waste management

This application allow high volume production of hydrogen. This will provide farmers with a significant revenue of their wastes. This application will involve a dark-fermentation step and a photo-fermentation step.

Applications

Domestic waste management

This application could be as an extension or an upgrade of an existing biogas facility to produce hydrogen and thus provide significant revenue to the process. This application could involve a dark-fermentation step and a photo-fermentation step.

Waste-water management

This application could provide significant revenue to other-wise expensive process of waste-water treatment. This would involve the photo-fermentation step integrated into an existing waste water treatment facility.

Example

- A production facility which produces 1 million m^3 hydrogen each year would require a dark-fermenter with a volume of 885 m^3 and a photo-fermenter with a volume of 650 m^3 .
- This facility will consume 217.000 tons of agricultural waste each year with a turnover of \$2.557 to \$11.073 for each ton of waste. This equals an annual turnover of \$555 million to \$2,4 billion each year.

Conclusion

- Industrial fermentation of hydrogen is a method to provide revenue to the process of waste treatment and to create new jobs in the country side.
- Industrial fermentation of hydrogen will lower the prices on hydrogen on the world market and reduce pollution world-wide.
- Industrial fermentation of hydrogen has a wide range of applications within waste treatment and can be integrated into any organic waste treatment process.
- Industrial fermentation of hydrogen will replace any existing hydrogen production because of the limited energy requirements in production.